

BC-SIM-TN-016

pacMan.sh User Manual

Version 1

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document describes the software PacMan.sh module used to build the frame images produced by the simAir program [RD.1] once elaborated a TeLeMetry (TLM) file for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory – SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS) instrument suite onboard the ESA mission BepiColombo to Mercury.

PacMan.sh assembles the frames image, decompresses it and store the information into the specific format (a table for housekeeping fields and an png image for the detectors data): these are the raw data where the HouseKeeping (HK) fields are (where needed) in physical units and the images of the detectors have the noise and possible artifacts that the detectors present (the images do not contain a calibrated data) and fill the PDS4 label.

1.2 Reference Document

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-TN-015 – simAir User Manual – Version 1 ,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8403037>
- [RD.2] BC-SIM-TN-003 – Reports and Notes Layout and Flow – Version 2,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)
- [RD.3] BC-SIM-GAF-IC-002 – SIMBYO-SYS Software Interface Control Document – rev. 14
- [RD.4] Image and Spectral image compression for four experiments on the ROSETTA and Mars Express missions of ESA. Y. Langevin and O. Forni, Institut d’Astrophysique spatiale, 91405 Orsay, France

1.3 Acronyms

DN	Digital Number
HK	HouseKeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
NAIF	Navigation and Ancillary Information Facility
PDS4	Planetary Data System version 4
SCOS-2000	Satellite Control and Operation System 2000
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SPICE	Spacecraft ephemeris, Planet, Instrument information, C-orientation, Events
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TC	TeleCommand
TLM	TeLeMetry
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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VIHI Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

1.4 Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.2] and will be archived both on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

Figure 1: PacMan.sh operating structure.

The *pachMan.sh* simplest execution command is:

```

pacMan.sh -input_folder output -output_folder results -preview -config_folder configData
-time_zero
  
```

3 Input and output

This paragraph describes the input options for *pacMan.sh*. The Table 1 lists the options and reports also examples of their using following the Figure 1 as example. A description of the output folder of *pacMan.sh* is provided.

3.1 Input

Table 1 lists all the *pacMan.sh* call options and an example of its usage.

Option name	Shortcut	Description and example
--help	-h	Print help and quit from the script
--input_folder	-d	Set the input folder to elaborate Example: --input_folder output
--output_folder	-o	Set the output folder with raw data in PDS4 format Example: --output_folder results
--preview	-p	A boolean setting: if set the program will generate also the images png and the ENVI hdr file, otherwise only PDS4 products will be generated. Example: --preview
--config_folder	-c	Set the folder where the file "config.xml" is stored. Example: --config_folder configData
--time_zero	-t	Set the time reference Example: --time_zero "Aug 22 1999 00:01:09"

Table 1: List of *pacMan.sh* program options.

3.2 Output

The *results* folder of Figure 1 is the output of *pacMan.sh*; in this folder there are:

- packets.log* which contains the list of "Source Packet Header" and "Packet Data Field" in csv format. Each column of the csv is a field of the packet headers.
- In *pacman.log* there are the list of actions performed by *pacMan.sh*.
- In the folders *stc*, *hric*, *vih* are stored the detector images in decompressed form and the calibrated housekeeping. The images are organized into folder called "*science_XXX*" where XXX is a counter form 0 to the number of acquisitions planned for the detector, the "*science_XXX*" folder are stored into *stc*, *hric* and *vih* folders..

3.3 Notes

3.3.1 Development environment

The software was developed into Linux system Fedora, and it is guaranteed its usability into CentOS 7 (environment agreed with ESA for the SIMBIO-SYS EGSE development).

3.3.2 The decompressor

As final step *pacMan.sh* calls an decompressor module that uses library described in [RD.4]. The module has the following options:

Option name	Shortcut	Description and example
--help	-h	Print help and quit from the script Example: <code>--help</code>
--image	-i	Set the input file name to elaborate Example: <code>--image frame_name.bin</code>
--xsize	-x	Set the number of pixel in column direction Example: <code>--xsize 256</code>
--ysize	-y	Set the number of pixel in row direction Example: <code>--ysize 256</code>
--ibr	-b	Set the Image Based Rendering; the possible value are in the range 0..63. Example: <code>--ibr 0</code>
--cdb	-c	Set the Compression Box value, the possible value are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 for subframe size 64x64 ▪ 2 for subframe size 128x64 ▪ 3 for subframe size 128x128 Example: <code>--cdb 1</code>
--channel	-l	Set channel to work with; the possible value are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 0 for VIHI ▪ 1 for STC and HRIC Example: <code>--channel 0</code>

Table 2 Decompressor program option and examples of usage.

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Before run *decompressor* program, *pacMan.sh* merges the subframe files, present in the sub directory of the *output* folder as described in [RD.1] , in unique frame file: this merged file is used as input to the *decompressor*. The options for the decompressor are extracted from the file name of the subframe.

4 Version

The current version of the software is 2.1.1.